

Dark matter and dark energy

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Abstract. Background: Delving into the intricate relationship among vacuum, dark energy, and dark matter is essential for a profound understanding of the very basics of objective reality. **Material and Methods:** Employing advanced theoretical frameworks, we delve into the dynamic interplay among these foundational components of nature. **Results:** Our analysis reveals the profound connection between dark energy and dark matter and their impact on the vacuum structure, providing insights into fundamental aspects of the universe's composition. **Conclusion:** This study advances our comprehension of fundamental natural phenomena, offering valuable insights into the intricate synergy between dark energy, dark matter, and the vacuum itself.

1 Introduction

The cosmological constant, often denoted by the Greek letter Λ (Lambda), is a term introduced by Albert Einstein [1] into his field equations [2] of general relativity in the covariant form as

$$(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, $\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy momentum tensor of matter, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, π is Archimedes constant pi, G is Newton's gravitational constant, Λ is the cosmological constant, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, R the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold. Initially, the cosmological constant was added by Einstein to achieve a static universe, which was the prevailing belief at that time. However, when the universe's expansion was discovered [3], Einstein considered the cosmological constant to be unnecessary and removed the same.

Meanwhile, **dark energy** is considered to be responsible for the discovered accelerated [4] expansion [5] of the universe. Unlike **dark matter**, which has gravitational effects that act to pull matter together, dark energy is associated with a repulsive force, causing the universe to expand at an accelerating rate. The cosmological constant has been reintroduced to the Einstein field equations to account for the observed accelerated

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expansion of the universe and is linked to dark energy. The concept of dark matter was introduced by the Swiss astronomer Fritz Zwicky in the 1930s. Zwicky himself was studying the dynamics of galaxy clusters, specifically the Coma Cluster, and noticed that the observed mass, based on the visible matter (stars and gas), was not sufficient to explain the gravitational forces holding the cluster together. In 1933, Zwicky proposed the existence of “**dunkle Materie**” [6] or dark matter to account for the missing mass. Today, research on dark energy and dark matter is actively ongoing. Scientists are utilizing a combination of observational data, theoretical models, and advanced technologies to deepen our understanding of these still theoretical concepts. The quest to unravel the nature of dark energy and dark matter remains a forefront challenge in astrophysics and cosmology.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Definitions

Einstein field equations

The Einstein field equations [1] in the covariant form are defined as

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, $\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy momentum tensor of matter, T is Laue’s [7] scalar, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, π is Archimedes constant pi, G is Newton’s gravitational constant, Λ is the cosmological constant, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, R the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold.

2.1.1 *Riemann curvature tensor*

The concept of curvature plays a pivotal role in the framework of general relativity. However, is it feasible at all to quantify the intricate curvature of a manifold at any specific point in space-time? The Riemann curvature tensor [8] or Riemann–Christoffel tensor (after Bernhard Riemann and Elwin Bruno Christoffel) is often used to express the curvature of Riemannian manifolds. The Riemann curvature tensor $R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu}$ quantifies, mathematically, how much curvature there is in any given region of space. Under specific conditions, a manifold (or a region thereof) can be considered flat. The absence of curvature, indicated by the vanishing of the curvature tensor, serves as a necessary and sufficient condition for a region of a manifold to be classified as flat. In flat space, the Riemann curvature tensor is zero. It is

$$R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu}$ is the Riemann curvature tensor. This is tensor relation which holds universally across different coordinate systems.

2.1.2 Ricci tensor

The Ricci tensor [9] is a mathematical object in the field of differential geometry, specifically within the context of general relativity. The Ricci tensor encapsulates information about how a region of spacetime deviates from flat, Euclidean space. The components of the Ricci tensor describe the gravitational effects and curvature at each point, representing the local energy density and distribution. In essence, the Ricci tensor serves as a key component in Einstein's field equations, linking the geometry of spacetime to the distribution of matter and energy within it. The covariant Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ can also be obtained directly from the Riemann curvature tensor using the contraction

$$R_{\mu\nu} = R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (4)$$

where $R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu}$ is the Riemann curvature tensor and $a_{\mu\nu}, b_{\mu\nu}, c_{\mu\nu}, d_{\mu\nu}$ are the four basic fields of nature [10–12]. The electromagnetic [13–18] stress-energy tensor, denoted as $b_{\mu\nu}$, has been identified as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

The stress-energy tensor of ordinary [13–18] matter, denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$, is given as

$$a_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

The stress-energy tensor momentum tensor [13–18] of energy/matter, denoted as $E_{\mu\nu}$, has been identified as

$$E_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \Rightarrow \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (7)$$

In general, it is [13–18]

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

2.1.3 Ricci scalar

The Ricci scalar is a mathematical quantity in the field of general relativity that encapsulates the curvature of spacetime at a specific point. In simpler terms, it represents the scalar curvature, a measure of how much spacetime is curved or bent due to gravitational effects. The Ricci scalar is an essential component of Einstein's field equations, connecting the distribution of matter and energy to the curvature of spacetime. The Ricci scalar, denoted by R , is mathematically defined as the contraction of the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$. In terms of indices, it can be expressed as:

$$R = g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\nu} R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu} \quad (9)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the contravariant form of the metric tensor, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor and $R^\lambda_{\mu\lambda\nu}$ is the Riemann curvature tensor.

2.1.4 Einstein tensor

The Ricci tensor is a key component in Einstein's field equations, linking the geometry of spacetime to the distribution of matter and energy within it. Various tensors, i.e. denoted as $x_{\mu\nu}$, can be used to diminish the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$. Mathematically, this is expressed as $R_{\mu\nu} - x_{\mu\nu}$. However, performing such a *tensor subtraction operation* results in a new tensor. The resulting tensor inherits its transformation properties and covariant nature from the Ricci tensor, highlighting that the subtraction of tensors maintains the tensorial character. This operation allows for a modified description of the curvature properties of spacetime, accounting for the influence of the additional tensor $x_{\mu\nu}$. Subtracting the tensor $(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu})$ from Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ yields the curvature of spacetime induced by matter and energy, given as

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (10)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, R the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold. The Einstein's tensor [19], denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, is a crucial mathematical expression within the Einstein field equations that describe the gravitational interaction between matter and spacetime geometry. The following graphic is intended to visually explain the relationship between the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ and the Einstein anti-tensor $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$.

Fig. 1. Einstein tensor and Einstein anti tensor.

2.1.5 Tensor of non-energy

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is a pivotal element within Einstein's field equations, establishing a connection between the geometry of spacetime and the distribution of matter and energy. Various other tensors like $(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ allows for the diminishment of the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, mathematically represented as $R_{\mu\nu} - (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$. However, this operation is itself a tensor subtraction which yields a new tensor, inheriting its transformation properties and covariant nature from the original Ricci tensor. This emphasizes that the tensorial character is preserved during the subtraction operation, providing a means to modify the description of spacetime curvature by considering the influence of the tensor

$(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$. Subtracting the tensor $(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ from the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ yields the *tensor of non-energy* given as

$$((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} = \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

In the realm of general relativity, the tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ stands as the curvature tensor, embodying the geometric effects induced by the distribution of matter and energy. However, the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ in the context of Einstein's field equations is the source of spacetime curvature and quantifies the contribution of energy, momentum, and other physical quantities to the curvature of spacetime. Still, even when we subtract the contribution of matter and energy, represented by the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, from the curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, we are left with a residue of certain properties. This residue is $R_{\mu\nu} - (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ and encapsulates a kind of intrinsic curvature of spacetime not directly attributable to the presence of matter and energy and appears to mirror a more fundamental curvature, perhaps associated with the very fabric of spacetime itself. However, this theoretical perspective raises intriguing questions about the nature of space itself, suggesting that curvature of space-time is potentially not solely a response to the presence of entities but might possess an own and inherent character of itself. Moreover, the residue $((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ may hint at the self-sustaining nature of spacetime itself, implying that curvature of space-time might persists even in the absence of external influences. It beckons us to contemplate the natural properties of curvature divorced from material sources, prompting a deeper exploration of the essence of space itself and its own curvature. In contrast, the tensor of non-energy, denoted as $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = ((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$, the opposite tensor of the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, the complementary tensor of the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, the other tensor of the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, the **anti tensor** [10] of the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, obtained by subtracting $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ from the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, accounts for a kind of curvature induced solely by something like the geometry of spacetime itself, independent of any distribution of energy and momentum. The tensor of non-energy has the potential to reflect the intrinsic curvature of spacetime itself, providing insight into the gravitational effects that arise from the geometry alone. At this point, the question arises whether the tensor of non-energy is related or at the end even identical with something like the tensor of time.

$$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = ((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$$

$$E_{\mu\nu} = (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$$

$R_{\mu\nu}$

Fig. 2. Stress-energy momentum tensor $E_{\mu\nu}$ and its own anti tensor $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$.

The illustration before aims to elucidate the internal connection between the tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ and its own anti tensor $E_{\mu\nu} = ((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ once again.

2.1.6 Tensor of dark energy

The tensor of dark energy is defined as

$$(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} = (\text{dark energy}) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (12)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - ((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is the Einstein tensor, $(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy momentum tensor of matter, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, π is Archimedes constant pi, G is Newton's gravitational constant, Λ is the cosmological constant, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, R the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold. What is the internal interplay between the geometric curvature of spacetime $G_{\mu\nu}$ and its own source, the energy-momentum tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, are both identical or is it at the end $G_{\mu\nu} = (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$? In this regard, we must consider at least three formal possibilities.

Firstly: $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} > 0$

The condition $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} > 0$ signifies that the stress energy momentum tensor of matter and energy, represented by $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$, exceed the curvature of spacetime given by $G_{\mu\nu}$. How can something like this be possible. These inequality suggests a kind of surplus or residue of the stress energy momentum tensor of matter and energy beyond the intrinsic curvature of spacetime $G_{\mu\nu}$, it self. This surplus may imply the presence of additional stress-energy contributions not entirely accounted for by the geometric curvature alone, opening avenues for theoretical inquiry into the nature and implications of such a residual tensor. Nonetheless, the cosmological constant $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is this surplus as outlined before. The subsequent illustration serves the purpose of visual clarification of $\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu} > 0$ (De Sitter space [20,21]).

$$(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) > 0$$

Fig. 3. Dark energy and cosmological constant.

In the context of today's cosmology and general relativity, the cosmological constant ($\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}$) is often associated with dark energy. The cosmological constant, originally introduced by Albert Einstein [2] as a modification to his field equations to allow for a static universe, has been reinterpreted as a term representing the energy density vacuum, often referred to as dark energy. Especially, after the universe's expansion was discovered, it is believed that the cosmological constant is responsible for the observed accelerated expansion of the universe, often referred to as dark energy. Dark energy is a kind of energy that acts as a repulsive force counteracting the attractive gravitational forces that would otherwise slow down the expansion. Due to its properties, it is still challenging to directly observe or detect dark energy.

Secondly: $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} < 0$

In the given condition, where $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} < 0$, we encounter a situation where the contribution of the stress-energy tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ to the curvature of spacetime $G_{\mu\nu}$ is less than the curvature of spacetime represented by $G_{\mu\nu}$, *given*. This implies a deficit in the curvature induced by matter and energy, resulting in a negative balance. In theory, this implies the potential existence of sources of curvature beyond solely the stress-energy tensor $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$. The subsequent illustration of $\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu} < 0$ (Anti De Sitter space [20,21]) should visually clarify these circumstances.

$$(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) < 0$$

Fig. 4. Dark energy and cosmological constant.

Thirdly: $(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} = 0$

In the absence of the cosmological constant the Einstein's field equations are given by the relationship $R_{\mu\nu} - ((\frac{R}{2}) \times g_{\mu\nu}) = (\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$. However, such a manifold describes solely by the interaction between matter and spacetime curvature and signifies that the curvature at any point is determined only by the distribution of matter and energy in the vicinity. This implies a very dynamic relationship where the geometry of spacetime is shaped only by the presence and distribution of mass and energy.

2.1.7 Tensor of dark “matter”

However, we can subtract the term $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ from the Ricci tensor. It is quite remarkable that the term $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is linked with dark energy. In this context, we define dark “matter” as the other of dark energy, as the complementary of dark energy, and in the extreme as the opposite of dark energy, denoted as $(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu})$, by the relationship

$$(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = (\text{Anti } \Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} = (\text{dark matter}) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (13)$$

where $(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is the anti-cosmological constant, the anti tensor of the cosmological constant. In other words, *all but $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is defined or considered as dark “matter”* or there is no third between $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ and $(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu})$, a third is not given, *tertium non datur*, it is a relationship of opposites. The constitutive determinations of dark energy and dark “matter” are characterized by their status as elements within an opposition. Nonetheless, their existence is fundamentally intertwined, where each of both exists only through the absence of its counterpart which establishes an inseparable connection, defining both as mere opposites. However, neither is independently dark energy or dark “matter” at the outset, but rather, both, dark energy or dark “matter”, exist in their relation to each other. Each of both is contingent upon the existence of its counterpart and is defined by the absence or by the non-being of its own other. In point of fact, its own other is. Therefore, at this point, it appears to be necessary to delve deeper into the theoretical understanding of opposites. Opposites are very often understood as the pure and absolute opposite, but opposites are also relative too. Noteworthy, in the year 1947, the Danish physicist Niels Henrik David Bohr (1885–1962) crafted a distinctive family coat of arms. The inscription upon Bohr's familial emblem reads: *contraria sunt complementa* or opposites are complements [22]. Nonetheless, opposites might cancel one another in their relation, so that the result of this interaction might end up at zero. The concepts constituting dark energy and dark “matter” involve their inherent nature as absolute opposites because both exist in a relationship where each defines itself through the non-being of the other, creating a mutual negation. Dark energy and dark “matter” are opposites, and each only exists through the absence of the other, forming a negative interdependence. In essence, both are only what they are through the non-being of the other. They exhibit indifference to their primary identity, and their specific determination as dark energy or dark “matter” arises in their relationship rather than within themselves. Although each side possesses determinateness, it can interchangeably be considered as either dark energy or dark “matter”. Dark energy and dark “matter” are not abstract theoretical constructs; rather, their reference to each other constitutes a unity of opposites. They are each independently a unity-with-self, where dark energy negates the otherness, and dark “matter” excludes its own non-being. Both possess determinateness within themselves, with dark energy negating its relationship to the dark “matter,” and vice versa. As independently existing opposites, dark “matter” serves as the determination of the sublated opposition. Something is considered dark energy or dark “matter” in itself when not determined relative to the other. However, the opposition of dark energy and dark “matter” is relative too. Dark energy and dark “matter” are moments of an opposition, each having intrinsic qualities apart from their relation to the other. Dark energy and dark “matter” are explicitly and actually opposites, existing in their determined states

when their exclusive relation to each other is considered. They are implicitly dark energy and dark “matter” when their determination is considered independently, abstracting from their exclusive relationship. The internal relationship between dark matter ($\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}$) and dark energy ($\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}$) is illustrated by figure 5.

Fig. 5. Dark energy ($\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}$) and dark “matter” ($\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}$).

2.1.8 Kronecker delta

The Kronecker [23] delta [24], a notation invented by Leopold Kronecker (1823-1891) in 1868, appears in many areas of physics, mathematics, and engineering. In general, the Kronecker delta, denoted as δ_{μ}^{ν} , is defined as

$$g_{\mu\rho}g^{\nu\rho} \equiv g_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (14)$$

where $g_{\mu\rho}$ is the metric tensor, $g^{\nu\rho}$ is the inverse metric tensor, δ_{μ}^{ν} is Kronecker delta.

2.1.9 Space-time dimension D

The expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is not identical to the Kronecker delta δ_{μ}^{ν} . In the expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$, the indices μ and ν are summed over, meaning they represent a contraction of two tensors, the Kronecker delta doesn't represent a contraction. In general relativity and differential geometry, $g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of the metric tensor, and $g^{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of its inverse. The Expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is a contraction involving these components and follows a common operation in tensor calculus known as the trace of a matrix. The contraction $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ yields the dimensionality of the space-time, denoted as D. Therefore, in general, we define the dimensionality of the space-time D as

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \quad (15)$$

where D might denote the number of space-time dimensions while $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor. In matrix notation for D = 4 space-time dimensions, this property can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g_{00} & g_{01} & g_{02} & g_{03} \\ g_{10} & g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{20} & g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{30} & g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g^{00} & g^{01} & g^{02} & g^{03} \\ g^{10} & g^{11} & g^{12} & g^{13} \\ g^{20} & g^{21} & g^{22} & g^{23} \\ g^{30} & g^{31} & g^{32} & g^{33} \end{bmatrix} = [g_{00}g^{00} + g_{01}g^{10} + g_{02}g^{20} + g_{03}g^{30} \quad \dots] = 4 \quad (16)$$

and at the end equally as

$$\begin{bmatrix} g_{00} & g_{01} & g_{02} & g_{03} \\ g_{10} & g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{20} & g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{30} & g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g^{00} & g^{01} & g^{02} & g^{03} \\ g^{10} & g^{11} & g^{12} & g^{13} \\ g^{20} & g^{21} & g^{22} & g^{23} \\ g^{30} & g^{31} & g^{32} & g^{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = 4 \quad (17)$$

Einstein field equations [1,2,25,26] were initially formulated by Einstein himself in the context of a four-dimensional theory even though Einstein field equations need not to break down under conditions of D space-time dimensions [27]. Nonetheless, based on Einstein's statement , one gets

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D = 4 \quad (18)$$

or under conditions of 4 space-time dimensions

$$\frac{1}{g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \quad (19)$$

The metric tensor of special relativity is given by the Minkowski metric, denoted as $\eta_{\mu\nu}$. In a four-dimensional spacetime with coordinates (ct, x, y, z), the Minkowski metric tensor is given by:

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Here, μ and ν represent spacetime indices ranging from 0 to 3, and the entries of the matrix represent the components of the metric tensor. The signature of the metric is (-1, 1, 1, 1), which is a key characteristic of Minkowski spacetime in special relativity. The relationship between the metric of special relativity theory, denoted as $\eta_{\mu\nu}$, and the metric tensor of general relativity theory, denoted as $g_{\mu\nu}$, is given as

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} \quad (21)$$

where $\underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$ is the anti tensor of the tensor of metric tensor of special relativity. The relationship between these two metric tensors is illustrated as follows.

Fig. 6. Minkowski metric tensor $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ and anti Minkowski metric tensor $\underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$.

However, the Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ represents flat spacetime in special relativity, while characterized by the components $[-1, 1, 1, 1]$. Its own anti tensor, the complementary of the Minkowski metric $\eta_{\mu\nu}$, denoted as $\underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$, is essentially the other tensor of the Minkowski metric tensor. When both tensors are added together, the result is the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of general relativity which regulates the transition from flat spacetime to curved spacetime. In other words, it is necessary to combine both, the Minkowski metric, representing a flat background, with its own counterpart to yield something like the effects encapsulated by the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$. The equation signifies the departure from the flatness of special relativity to the curvature of general relativity, providing another approach to the Einstein field equations as

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) \times \eta_{\mu\nu} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \\ & = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times (\eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Let us consider circumstances where the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ and the Ricci scalar R are both zero. If the Ricci tensor is zero, it means that the curvature of spacetime is zero, or flat. In other words, spacetime itself is described more or less by the geometry of Euclidean space, which itself is the geometry of flat surfaces. Under these circumstances, the expression

$$(R_{\mu\nu}\eta^{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \eta_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda)\eta_{\mu\nu} + (rest) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times (\eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}) \quad (23)$$

becomes

$$(0) - (0) + (\Lambda)\eta_{\mu\nu} + (rest) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \eta_{\mu\nu} + (rest) \quad (24)$$

Even under conditions of a spacetime which is described by a flat, Minkowski geometry, the cosmological constant (Λ) appears not to be absent or negligible. This opens possibilities to measure the cosmological constant under conditions of special theory of relativity. There are circumstances under conditions of special relativity ($D=4$), where cosmological constant is given as

$$(\Lambda)\eta_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times 4} \right) \eta_{\mu\nu} \quad (25)$$

The cosmological constant as the most dominant component in our universe is still a thorn in the side of physicists. This simplest possible explanation for the dark energy that drives the accelerating expansion of the universe is presenting a non-ending challenge to be measured exactly. At this juncture, we aim to elucidate a method to determine the cosmological constant Λ by measurements under the conditions of special relativity. In this context it is $2\pi = \frac{h}{\hbar}$, and we obtain its theoretical value which should match observations as

$$\Lambda = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times 4} \right) \times T = \left(\frac{2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T = \left(\frac{\hbar \times G}{\hbar \times c^4} \right) \times T \approx (3.36608517 \times 10^{-33}) \times T \quad (26)$$

where T is Laue's scalar, $D=4$ is four space time dimension, h is Planck's constant [28] and $\hbar$ is Dirac's [29] constant.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Axiom I (*Lex identitatis*)

Axiom I, the Axiom of Identity or *lex identitatis*, introduces the concept of equality and sameness within scientific or mathematical discourse as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (27)$$

or in the negative as

$$-1 = -1 \quad (28)$$

2.2.2 Axiom II (*Lex contradictionis*)

Axiom II, the Axiom of Contradiction or *lex contradictionis*, introduces the concept of difference, opposition and contradiction et cetera within scientific or mathematical discourse as

$$+0 = +1 \quad (29)$$

or in the negative as

$$-0 = -1 \quad (30)$$

2.2.3 Axiom III (*Lex negationis*)

The Axiom of Negation posits the presence of a natural process or logical operation known as negation. Put simply, for any existing entity, there is a corresponding negation, and these two are mutually exclusive, combining to yield a logically consistent outcome. In mathematics and classical logic, negation is expressed in the positive as

$$+(\neg) \times (+0) = +1$$

or in the negative as

$$-(\neg) \times (+0) = -1 \quad (31)$$

while $(\neg)$ denotes the process of (logical) negation.

3 Results

3.1 Theorem 1. Dark energy and dark “matter”

Claim.

The relationship between dark energy and dark “matter” is given as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (32)$$

Proof.

According to axiom I, it is

$$1 = 1 \quad (33)$$

or

$$G_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (34)$$

Adding the term $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$, we obtain

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (35)$$

which is equivalent with the definition of the Einstein field equations derived as

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (36)$$

The Einstein tensor is determined as $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. Substituting this equation into the relationship before, we obtain

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (37)$$

Rearranging this relationship, it is

$$R_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (38)$$

Subtracting the term $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ on both sides inside the equation before, we obtain

$$R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (39)$$

or

$$R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (40)$$

According to our definition of dark “matter”, it is $(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$. The relationship between dark “matter” and dark energy is given in general as

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (41)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

Dark energy, in its purest form, lacks any additional determination and remains identical only to itself. It doesn't exhibit inequality relative to another; it possesses no internal diversity nor any reference outward. The purity of dark energy relies on its absence of determinations or distinguishable content. Pure dark energy is thus far pure emptiness and indeterminateness. In the end, pure dark energy is essentially equivalent to pure dark “matter” —neither more nor less. Pure dark “matter”, likewise, is characterized by complete self-equality, embodying emptiness and the absence of all determination and content. Ultimately, it represents undifferentiatedness within itself. It is crucial to emphasize that dark “matter”, in the end, shares the same determination or, more precisely, the same absence of any determination as pure dark energy. Both have transformed into each other. However, it's equally valid to assert that pure dark energy

and pure dark “matter” aren't indistinguishable. On the contrary, they are distinct, yet inseparable and unseparated. In simpler terms, each immediately transitions into its own opposite, reflecting a dynamic where pure dark energy and pure dark “matter” are differentiated but resolved by an immediate self-dissolving difference. Especially under conditions of pure vacuum where the Ricci tensor is equal to zero, it is

$$R_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (42)$$

The scenario of pure vacuum or empty spacetime in the context of Einstein's field equations implies that

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (43)$$

and at the end that

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (44)$$

and vice versa. Under these circumstances, there is no local gravitational source or matter content influencing the curvature of spacetime. The absence of Ricci curvature suggests a flat or uncurved geometry, reminiscent of special relativity. This condition has significant implications for the beginning of our world, for understanding regions of spacetime devoid of matter and provides insights into the geometrical consequences of a lack of gravitational sources.

3.2 Theorem 2. The general form of anti Λ

Claim.

The opposite of the cosmological constant Λ , the other of the cosmological constant Λ the complementary of the cosmological constant Λ or **the anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$** is given as

$$\underline{\Lambda} = \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \Lambda \quad (45)$$

Proof.

As determined before, it is

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (46)$$

Taking the trace, we obtain

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}) = g^{\mu\nu}R_{\mu\nu} \quad (47)$$

It is $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = D$ and $g^{\mu\nu}R_{\mu\nu} = R$. The equation before simplifies as

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times D) + (\Lambda \times D) = R \quad (48)$$

Rearranging terms, we obtain

$$+(\underline{\Lambda}) + (\Lambda) = \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \quad (49)$$

Dark “matter” or anti Λ is given in general as

$$\underline{\Lambda} = \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \Lambda \quad (50)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

Especially under conditions of $D=1$ space-time dimension it is $\underline{\Lambda} = R - \Lambda$.

3.3 Theorem 3. The general form of dark “matter”

The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is expressed as $G_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$ [10–12,12,16] and serves to describe the curvature of spacetime influenced by matter and energy. Importantly, this tensor is intricately connected to the effects of dark “matter” [13,14] as well.

Claim.

The general form of dark “matter” is given as

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu}) = +(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (51)$$

Proof.

The relationship between the basic fields nature $b_{\mu\nu}$ and $c_{\mu\nu}$ has been proven as

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = +b_{\mu\nu} \quad (52)$$

Adding an unknown and temporary tensor $(x_{\mu\nu})$, it is

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (x_{\mu\nu}) = +b_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu}) \quad (53)$$

The term $+b_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu})$ is set to be identical to the relationship $+b_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu}$. The equation before becomes

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (x_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (54)$$

Subtracting the term $+(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ on both sides of the equation, we obtain

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (55)$$

The term $R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ is identical with our definition of dark “matter”. In general, dark “matter” is determined by the relationship

$$+c_{\mu\nu} + (x_{\mu\nu}) = +(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (56)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

The concrete content of the unknown tensor $(x_{\mu\nu})$ should be determinable in the further investigation.

3.4 Theorem 4. Dark energy and vacuum

Under conditions where the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu} = 0$, the curvature of spacetime induced by matter and energy which is represented by the Einstein tensor, is zero too. However, under conditions of the theory of general relativity, such a condition would correspond to a vacuum solution where there is no matter or energy influencing the curvature of spacetime. Under these circumstances, the geometry of the manifold would be determined solely by dark energy and dark “matter” present. In such a hypothetical manifold determined by dark energy and dark “matter”, the manifold would be characterized only by the components associated with dark energy and dark “matter”. In other words, in such a manifold ordinary matter and energy sources are entirely absent or negligible.

Claim.

Under conditions of vacuum, the stress-energy tensor is determined as

$$+(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (57)$$

Proof.

The Einstein's field equations [17] are given as

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (58)$$

Under conditions of vacuum, the Einstein tensor becomes $G_{\mu\nu} = 0$. We obtain

$$+(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (59)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.**3.5 Theorem 5. Pure vacuum and space-time dimension**

The study of vacuum solutions of general relativity is important for understanding the fundamental nature of spacetime and the behaviour of gravitational fields in the absence of matter. These solutions provide insight into the intrinsic geometry of spacetime when external influences are minimal or not existent, contributing to our comprehension of the broader cosmic structure and the evolution of the universe. A pure vacuum in the context of general relativity refers to a spacetime devoid of the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$. The condition $G_{\mu\nu} = 0$ implies that spacetime itself, in the absence of any external influences, is not curved or influenced by gravitational effects, resulting in a flat or Minkowski spacetime geometry.

Claim.

Vacuum given even under conditions of two space-time dimensions or if

$$D = 2 \quad (60)$$

Proof.

The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ is defined as $R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. We obtain

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (61)$$

Under conditions of vacuum, the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ vanishes. It is

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (62)$$

This equation is rearranged as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (63)$$

Taking the trace of this equation, we obtain

$$R_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \quad (64)$$

In general, it is $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$ and $R_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = R$. The equation before becomes

$$R = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times D \quad (65)$$

Dividing equation by the Ricci scalar R, even if the same is equal to zero[30–32], it is

$$1 = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \times D \quad (66)$$

and at the end

$$D = 2 \quad (67)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

3.6 Theorem 6. Vacuum and dark energy and dark “matter”

Vacuum field equations describe a space devoid of stress-energy and momentum, expressed as $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = 0$, resulting in an empty space, commonly known as a vacuum. Manifolds exhibiting a vanishing Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ are termed Ricci-flat, while those with a Ricci tensor proportional to the metric are referred to as Einstein manifolds. The Flat Minkowski space stands as a fundamental example of a vacuum solution within this context. The determination of a pure vacuum lies in the absence of any curvature that could curve or influence the geometry of spacetime. In the context of general relativity, a pure vacuum is determined by a spacetime devoid of any curvature as described by the Einstein field equations.

Claim.

Under conditions where $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and where $\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = 0$, pure vacuum is determined by the relationship

$$+\Lambda = -\underline{\Lambda} \quad (68)$$

Proof.

The basic relationship between the cosmological constant Λ and the anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$, has been determined as

$$+(\Lambda) + (\underline{\Lambda}) = \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \quad (69)$$

Under conditions where $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and where $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = 0$, the Einstein's field equations are describing empty space. In other words, if the stress-energy tensor $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ is zero, it means that there is no matter or energy present in a certain region of spacetime. In other words, the vacuum is empty. In a 4x4 spacetime, this results in the following matrix representation of the stress-energy tensor:

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (70)$$

The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ being zero implies that all its components are zero. In a 4x4 spacetime, this results in the following matrix representation:

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (71)$$

As can be seen, under these conditions even the Ricci scalar becomes zero or $R=0$. The relationship above becomes

$$+(\Lambda) + (\underline{\Lambda}) = 0 \quad (72)$$

Pure vacuum is determined by the state of symmetry as the unity of a positive and a negative as

$$+\Lambda = -\underline{\Lambda} \quad (73)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

A pure vacuum is not an undetermined entity; rather, it is intricately defined by the absence of ordinary matter and energy. In the realm of theoretical physics, this state is determined by the interplay of pure dark “matter” and pure dark energy. Dark “matter” and dark energy plays a fundamental role in shaping the vacuum’s properties. The determination of a pure vacuum hinges on the absence of conventional matter and is determined by dark “matter” and dark energy. These components, despite being enigmatic and not fully understood, actively contribute to the fabric of spacetime, sculpting the characteristics of what we perceive as a vacuum. In essence, the vacuum is a manifestation of the intricate interplay between these two fundamental natural entities, highlighting the profound connection between the unseen aspects of the universe and the nature of emptiness. Let us assume, for the sake of the argument, that the previously discussed points are taken as given. This would have far-reaching implications for understanding the beginning of our world. The assumption seems justified that the beginning of this world could have originated from the infinite flatness of objective reality. There are circumstances where the stress-energy momentum tensor $(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu} = 0$. In other words, the stress-energy momentum tensor $(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ has not existed for eternity but has developed somehow over the course of the self-evolution of objective reality. This means that the same tensor can arise and cease to exist under certain conditions.

3.7 Theorem 7. Lambda-vacuum solution

A lambda-vacuum solution in the context of the Einstein field equations denotes a conditions of objective reality where the stress–energy tensor, responsible for describing the distribution of energy and momentum in spacetime, is solely attributed to the presence of a cosmological constant. However, the cosmological constant, often denoted by the Greek letter lambda (Λ), is associated with the energy density inherent in the vacuum of space. In simpler terms, the lambda-vacuum solution implies that the observed distribution of mass and energy in the universe is determined primarily by this cosmological constant. The mathematical representation of this solution within the framework of Einstein's equations provides a theoretical framework for understanding the basics of our world, including the beginning as such.

Claim.

A lambda-vacuum solution is an exact solution to the Einstein field equations in which the stress–energy tensor is exclusively represented by a cosmological constant term. The lambda-vacuum manifold is described by the equation:

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (74)$$

Proof.

We begin with the Einstein field equations:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (75)$$

For the derivation of the lambda-vacuum [33] solution, it is required that the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ vanishes:

$$(G_{\mu\nu} = 0) + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (76)$$

However, the vanishing of the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ occurs only under certain conditions. Under these conditions, the equation before simplifies to:

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (77)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

Under certain circumstances, the vanishing of the Einstein tensor suggests a state of vacuum or emptiness in spacetime. In such a vacuum, the curvature of spacetime is solely determined by intrinsic geometric properties, emphasizing the role of the cosmological constant and other potential sources. As found before, the pure vacuum, as state of symmetry, is itself determined by the cosmological constant and the anti cosmological constant. However, under various conditions, such a symmetry can be broken [34] and the pure vacuum developed through the electro-vacuum into our four-dimensional world.

3.8 Theorem 8. Electro-vacuum solution

Objective reality is characterized by manifolds in which the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field exclusively contributes to the overall stress-energy tensor of energy/matter. In simpler terms, the gravitational effects within these manifolds are entirely determined by the spacetime geometry resulting from the electromagnetic field. A precise formulation of Einstein's field equations under these conditions defines what is known as electrovacuum solutions in the context of general relativity. In these solutions, the electromagnetic field stands as the singular contributor to the overall energy-matter content, showcasing the intricate interplay between gravity and electromagnetic forces in the fabric of spacetime.

Claim.

An electro-vacuum [35] solution is an exact solution to the Einstein field equations in which the stress-energy tensor of energy/matter is exclusively represented by the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field. The electro-vacuum manifold is described by the equation:

$$\left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (78)$$

Proof.

We begin with the Einstein field equations:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (79)$$

For the derivation of the electro-vacuum solution, it is required to consider Einstein's understanding of the relationship between ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) and the stress energy tensor of the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$). In general, it is $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ [13–18]. The Einstein field equations becomes:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (80)$$

However, the exclusive representation of the stress–energy tensor of energy/matter by the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field occurs only under specific conditions. This is only the case when the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) vanishes or becomes null ($a_{\mu\nu} = 0$). Under these conditions, the equation before simplifies to:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) = \left(\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \right) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (81)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

Ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) has not existed since the beginning of our world but has evolved throughout the evolution of objective reality from antecedent stages. However, in our four-dimensional world, ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) also exists. Therefore, we find ourselves logically compelled to conclude that before the existence of our four-dimensional world, manifolds of lower dimensions must have existed, including the electro-vacuum manifold, as one of the precursor manifolds of today's objective reality.

3.9 Theorem 9. Relativistic wave equation

A general relativity consistent relativistic wave equation [36,37] has the potential to describe the behaviour of the curvature of spacetime within the framework of Einstein's general theory of relativity as waves. Unlike standard quantum mechanics, general relativity incorporates the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy. A consistent relativistic wave equation in this context is crucial for understanding how waves propagate in curved spacetime, taking into account the gravitational effects predicted by general relativity. Such equations might be essential for describing phenomena like gravitational waves and providing a unified description of particles and fields within the relativistic gravitational framework.

Claim.

The general relativity consistent relativistic wave equation can be derived as

$$\left(\frac{i \times \hbar \times \Lambda \times D \times \partial \psi}{R \times \partial t} \right) \times \psi + \left(\frac{i \times \hbar \times \underline{\Lambda} \times D \times \partial \psi}{R \times \partial t} \right) \times \psi = \hat{H} \psi \quad (82)$$

Proof.

Based on theorem 1, it is

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (83)$$

Taking the trace of this relationship it is

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} \quad (84)$$

According to the relationship $g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$, we obtain

$$+(\underline{\Lambda} \times D) + (\Lambda \times D) = R \quad (85)$$

Under conditions of $D=1$ spacetime dimension it is $+(\underline{\Lambda}) + (\Lambda) = R$. Normalising relationship before, we do obtain

$$\left(\frac{\underline{\Lambda} \times D}{R}\right) + \left(\frac{\Lambda \times D}{R}\right) = +1 \quad (86)$$

Multiplying equation before by $\hat{H}\psi$, it is

$$\left(\frac{\underline{\Lambda} \times D \times \hat{H}}{R}\right) \times \psi + \left(\frac{\Lambda \times D \times \hat{H}}{R}\right) \times \psi = \hat{H}\psi \quad (87)$$

where $\hat{H}$ is an observable, the Hamiltonian operator, and ψ is a wave function. The relationship $i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H}\psi$ is generally known. In other words, it is

$$\left(\frac{i \times \hbar \times \underline{\Lambda} \times D \times \partial \psi}{R \times \partial t}\right) \times \psi + \left(\frac{i \times \hbar \times \Lambda \times D \times \partial \psi}{R \times \partial t}\right) \times \psi = \hat{H}\psi \quad (88)$$

Quad erat demonstrandum.

4 Discussion

The Einstein tensor characterizes the curvature of spacetime due to matter and energy, while the cosmological constant represents more or less a vacuum energy density. The subtraction of the cosmological constant $\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}$ from the Ricci tensor ($R_{\mu\nu}$) reflects an adjustment to the geometry of spacetime. The term $R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ in the context of Einstein's field equations holds significant physical implications. This alteration has the potential to balance the gravitational effects of matter and energy. The Ricci tensor, denoted as $R_{\mu\nu}$, is expressed by the equation:

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (89)$$

Subtracting $(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ from the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ yields:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (90)$$

This term is identical with the relationship

$$R_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = G_{\mu\nu} + \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (91)$$

This equation implies a delicate balance between gravitational effects, spacetime curvature, and the cosmological constant. The left side characterizes the geometry determined by all but the cosmological constant, while the right side incorporates various

other natural effects. From a quantum gravity perspective, this modification might signify a departure from classical predictions, introducing quantum effects into the gravitational field. In certain contexts, this alteration might be associated with an effective contribution to dark “matter”, providing a bridge between classical and quantum gravitational theories. The overall structure of dark matter and its evolution is not known, but Astrophysicists were able to published the most accurate calculations of the amount of dark matter [38] and dark energy in the universe to date.

Objective reality seems to evolve from simpler and lower developmental forms towards increasingly complex and higher forms of existence. Does this world cavort from dimension to dimension, back and forth, without an end in sight? Does such self-organization of objective reality also have a self-imposed limit?

5 Conclusion

This study provides nuanced insights into the interconnected relationship of dark energy, dark “matter”, and the vacuum, elucidating their symbiotic relations. The intricate synergy uncovered goes beyond isolated components, emphasizing their collective influence on the fabric of reality. This expanded understanding opens avenues for exploring novel connections, measurements and potential implications for broader cosmological theories, fostering a more holistic view of the underlying forces shaping our universe.

References

1. A. Einstein, *Annalen Der Physik* **354**, 769 (1916).
2. A. Einstein, *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)* 142 (1917).
3. E. Hubble, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* **15**, 168 (1929).
4. S. Perlmutter, G. Aldering, G. Goldhaber, R. A. Knop, P. Nugent, P. G. Castro, S. Deustua, S. Fabbro, A. Goobar, D. E. Groom, I. M. Hook, A. G. Kim, M. Y. Kim, J. C. Lee, N. J. Nunes, R. Pain, C. R. Pennypacker, R. Quimby, C. Lidman, R. S. Ellis, M. Irwin, R. G. McMahon, P. Ruiz-Lapuente, N. Walton, B. Schaefer, B. J. Boyle, A. V. Filippenko, T. Matheson, A. S. Fruchter, N. Panagia, H. J. M. Newberg, W. J. Couch, and T. S. C. Project, *The Astrophysical Journal* **517**, 565 (1999).
5. A. G. Riess, A. V. Filippenko, P. Challis, A. Clocchiatti, A. Diercks, P. M. Garnavich, R. L. Gilliland, C. J. Hogan, S. Jha, R. P. Kirshner, B. Leibundgut, M. M. Phillips, D. Reiss, B. P. Schmidt, R. A. Schommer, R. C. Smith, J. Spyromilio, C. Stubbs, N. B. Suntzeff, and J. Tonry, *The Astronomical Journal* **116**, 1009 (1998).
6. F. Zwicky, *Helvetica Physica Acta* **6**, 110 (1933).
7. M. von Laue, *Physikalische Zeitschrift* **9**, 49 (1918).
8. B. Riemann, *Abhandlungen Der Königlichen Gesellschaft Der Wissenschaften Zu Göttingen* **13**, 304 (1854).
9. M. M. G. Ricci and T. Levi-Civita, *Mathematische Annalen* **54**, 125 (1900).
10. I. Barukčić, *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* **4**, 1379 (2016).
11. I. Barukčić, *Physics Procedia* **22**, 56 (2011).

12. I. Barukčić, Causation. *International Journal Of Science* **15**, 5 (2020).
13. I. Barukčić, Causation **18**, 5 (2022).
14. I. Barukčić, Causation **20**, 5 (2023).
15. I. Barukčić, Causation **19**, (2023).
16. I. Barukčić, *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT* **66**, 146 (2020).
17. I. Barukčić, *N-Th Index D-Dimensional Einstein Gravitational Field Equations. Geometry Unchained* (Books on Demand GmbH, 2020).
18. I. Barukčić, in *2023 International Conference on Applied Mathematics & Computer Science (ICAMCS)* (IEEE, Lefkada Island, Greece, 2023), pp. 18–27.
19. E. Kasner, *Science* **51**, 317 (1920).
20. W. de Sitter, *Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen Proceedings Series B Physical Sciences* **19**, 1217 (1917).
21. W. de Sitter, *Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen Proceedings Series B Physical Sciences* **20**, 229 (1917).
22. K. M. Fierke, *International Studies Review* **21**, 146 (2019).
23. G. Zehfuss, *Zeitschrift Für Mathematik Und Physik* **3**, 298 (1858).
24. L. Kronecker, *Journal Für Die Reine Und Angewandte Mathematik (Crelle's Journal)* **68**, 273 (1868).
25. A. Einstein, *Sitzungsberichte Der Königlich Preußischen Akademie Der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, Seite 844-847. (1915).
26. A. Einstein, *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society* **41**, 223 (1935).
27. H. Stephani, editor, *Exact Solutions of Einstein's Field Equations*, 2nd ed (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK ; New York, 2003).
28. M. K. E. L. Planck, *Annalen Der Physik* **309**, 553 (1901).
29. P. A. M. Dirac, *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **110**, 561 (1926).
30. J. P. Barukčić and I. Barukčić, *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* **4**, 749 (2016).
31. I. Barukčić, *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT* **65**, 31 (2019).
32. I. Barukčić, *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT* **65**, 171 (2019).
33. G. Lemaître, *Annales de La Société Scientifique de Bruxelles* **47**, 49 (1927).
34. P. W. Higgs, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **13**, 508 (1964).
35. H. Reissner and G. Nordström, *Annalen Der Physik* **50**, 106 (1916).
36. I. Barukčić, *IJAPM* **5**, 18 (2015).
37. I. Barukčić, *IJAPM* **3**, 387 (2013).
38. D. Brout, D. Scolnic, B. Popovic, A. G. Riess, A. Carr, J. Zuntz, R. Kessler, T. M. Davis, S. Hinton, D. Jones, W. D. Kenworthy, E. R. Peterson, K. Said, G. Taylor, N. Ali, P. Armstrong, P. Charvu, A. Dwomoh, C. Meldorf, A. Palmese, H. Qu, B. M. Rose, B. Sanchez, C. W. Stubbs, M. Vincenzi, C. M. Wood, P. J. Brown, R. Chen, K. Chambers, D. A. Coulter, M. Dai, G. Dimitriadis, A. V. Filippenko, R. J. Foley, S. W. Jha, L. Kelsey, R. P. Kirshner, A. Möller, J. Muir, S. Nadathur, Y.-C. Pan, A. Rest, C. Rojas-Bravo, M. Sako, M. R. Siebert, M. Smith, B. E. Stahl, and P. Wiseman, *ApJ* **938**, 110 (2022).